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Using Digital Tools in Teaching Russian Language and Literature at School

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Abstract

The relevance of research is due to changes characterizing the modern educational space. High-quality education should be provided with the opportunity to build an individual route, relying on the experience of the subject, and access to digital tools. Using all the possibilities of digital space requires the ability to work with various resources, presented both in the usual "paper" and in the new digital format.

In this regard, this article is aimed at research of studying the issues caused by insufficient research on the impact of Internet communications on personality development, the processes of education and training of students; determining the relationship between technological and ethical aspects of digital ownership; goals and forms of interaction of the teacher with the student in digitalization; technologies for organizing educational activities using digital tools; quality educational media content; designing a scientifically based teacher pedagogical support strategy.

The article provides and analyzes specific examples of the use of digital tools in the lessons of the Russian language and literature in primary and high school, describes the advantages and disadvantages of different forms of interaction. Practical significance is determined by the focus on designing the experience of using digital tools by a language teacher. The study confirms the inefficiency of a complete rejection of traditional methodological resources in connection with the axiological component of Russian language and literature courses. The necessity of an integrated approach to the study of the problem together with specialists from other branches of pedagogical sciences is emphasized.

The research methods are the conceptualization of concepts, the critical interpretation method, and the survey method.

Keywords: digital tools in teaching, teacher training, teacher of Russian language and literature, language teacher, Russian language, Russian literature.

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Introduction

The modern educational system is characterized by the multiplicity of discourse, interpretation, openness, eclecticism, pluralism, interdisciplinarity, non-linearity. These features are manifested to varying degrees, but in all countries of the world: individual construction of content, reliance on the subject's experience, variability of content, variability is vital to quality education. The digital educational environment has been considered not only as a platform for the formation of subject-specific skills anymore, but also as a means of forming functional literacy (Rusitoru et al., 2016), ensuring the successful mastery of meta-subject and work skills in the information and educational environment. Modern sociological research confirms “the massive and purposeful use of the Internet space, educationally oriented computer programs of various types: actually teaching, applied, instrumental telecommunications - with the goal of creating an integrated learning environment” (Aleksandrova et al., 2018), which allows intensively developing the speech-cognitive abilities of students, increasing their cognitive motivation. Today in the training of Russian language teachers we take into account new ways of transmitting information and organizing interaction: studying via digital materials: instructions, recommendations, texts, video lectures; the study of text; visualization of linguistic and didactic information, the creation of a digital lesson plan, the making of digital references, comments on language assignments, a detailed assessment, etc. Nevertheless, without one's mastering the basic tools in the sphere of information processing of a text, the internalization of information would fail to occur (Dobrotina, 2016).

In fact, applying to digital tools, allows you to use the ability and desire of students to work in the information space, acquire new knowledge, based on their own experience.

In accordance with the “National Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence for the period until 2030” (Presidential Decree, 2019), the issues of “developing and implementing educational modules in the framework of educational programs at all levels of education, continuing education programs and retraining for citizens to acquire knowledge and acquire competencies are becoming relevant for all educational institutions” and skills in mathematics, programming, data analysis, machine learning, contributing to the development of artificial intelligence lecture. It is highlighted that "convergent knowledge is gaining priority, which is provided, inter alia, through the integration of mathematical, natural-scientific and social-humanitarian education."

Purpose and objectives of the study

Today's educational space is characterized by accessibility of nearly any sources of information, by versatility of means of getting access to knowledge and cultural values, and by an opportunity to exchange information, including information that has been processed by parties involved in educational activities according to their academic objectives. However, the biggest problem does not lie in the use of a channel of receiving information and not even in finding relevant sources but in the skill to identify, in an abundance of information, what you need to have in order to perform some specific activity, and to absorb the right type of information and in the right quantity to address real-life problems. Schoolchildren have found themselves in a situation where they need to manage ever-increasing volumes of information flows, including those represented in the digital form.

However, there are a number of problems caused by the lack of research on the impact of Internet communications on personality development, educating and nurturing children; determining the relationship between technological and ethical aspects of digital ownership; goals and forms of interaction teachers and students in digitalization; technologies for organizing educational activities using digital tools; quality educational media content; designing a scientifically based teacher pedagogical support strategy.

It is important to understand the extent to which the use of digital tools in teaching Russian language and literature in the primary school meets the objectives and provides support in the education of the linguistic identity of students.

Literature review

Research in all areas is carried out from the standpoint of both theoretical and practical developments. Theoretical positions were reflected in a number of publications by laboratory scientists in domestic and foreign publications, speeches at international conferences, forums, symposia. They are dedicated to the issues of updating school literary education in a post-industrial society (Aristova et al., 2017); the definition of the term "educational text" in the conditions of the information and educational environment (Aleksandrova et al., 2017); a list of skills in the information environment (Alexandrova et al., 2018a) and ways to build reader literacy (Alexandrova et al., 2018b).

There is research on the readiness of Russian teachers to use digital technologies in the teaching-learning process (Ajmaletdinov et al., 2019); teachers are encouraged to assess their own digital competence.

Having gained some experience using the Moodle platform, which is focused on collaborative learning technologies, they continue to search for solutions to the organization of education as a cooperative achievement of learning objectives (Narushevich, 2012). Integration of teachers' fundamental psychological and pedagogical knowledge and practical skills in the digital learning environment is a principal defining factor. Currently, professional training of students of Moscow Region State University is carried out as part of the research (task) system for the training of Russian language teachers (Gats, 2018).

During the expert session "Modern Textbook: Fundamental Science and Teaching Practice", which was held at the initiative of the Federal State Budgetary Institution "Institute for the Development of Education of the Russian Academy of Education" in the Public Chamber of the Russian Federation in November 2018, the need for research on a number of fundamental scientific problems was noted, among which: the ratio of different ways of presenting information in a modern school textbook; synergetics of fundamental science and teaching practice in a modern textbook; the place and role of the textbook as a basic component of the teaching materials in modeling the modern information and educational environment; the problem of pedagogical examination of a modern textbook; the function of the electronic textbook in the modern educational process; reflection of the country's history in the school history textbook and others. Participants spoke about the relevance of the study of the correlation of the paper-based textbook and the electronic-format textbook, noting the importance of studying the role of digital pedagogy and game gamification of education. The need was emphasized to study both the new opportunities offered by electronic educational resources and the risks arising from this.

Methodology

The article provides and analyzes specific examples of the use of digital tools in the lessons of the Russian language and literature in primary and high school, describes the advantages and disadvantages of different forms of interaction. Practical significance is determined by the focus on designing the experience of using digital tools by a language teacher. The study confirms the inefficiency of a complete rejection of traditional methodological resources in connection with the axiological component of Russian language and literature courses. The necessity of an integrated approach to the study of the problem together with specialists from other branches of pedagogical sciences is emphasized.

The main methods of the undertaken research were content analysis, systematization of the results of pedagogical and methodological scientific research in order to determine the degree of knowledge of the problem; generalization of author's experience in creating textbooks and teaching aids; reflection of their own scientific and pedagogical activity.

The task of updating the content of school language and literary education is determined by the changing socio-political conditions and requests of participants in the educational process, as well as the need for the most complete implementation of the requirements of the Federal State Educational Standard. The openness and accessibility of information, the development of academic mobility, the possibility of widespread interaction in the global cultural and educational space, characteristic of the modern post-industrial society, create favorable conditions for the development of school education in the field of philological cycle subjects.

The research carried out by the laboratory of philological general education made it possible to ascertain that one of the promising areas in this area is updating the scientific foundations of the subject based on the achievements of modern philology, the hallmark of which is the desire for interdisciplinarity. Another important direction of updating the content of school education in the subjects of the philological cycle is the strengthening of attention to the culturological component of the subjects studied and the formation of the general cultural competence of students. Studies by both domestic and foreign scholars point out an alarming situation that is recognized as a global trend: the loss of cultural values, national "cultural codes", which is reflected, in particular, in widening the gap between the modern student and the culture of the past. It is possible to overcome this negative trend if we actualize the cultural potential of the educational material that makes up the content of the subjects of the philological cycle, draw the attention of students to intercultural dialogue, which allows us to establish connections and interactions between different peoples and countries using the language and literature studied, understand and accept other national cultural traditions, customs and foundations. The third area of research is the determination of the possibility of subjects "Russian language" and "literature" in the process of formation of functional literacy, which ensures the successful mastery of meta-subject and work skills in the information and educational environment.

Results

Laboratory staff analyzed some educational resources, taking into account the target group, the need for registration/conditions, compliance with the sample program, the possibility of modeling a lesson/training session, the availability of criteria/verification/ feedback; conclusions are made about the possibility of using resources to organize distance learning for students.

"My Achievements" service - online self-study and self-test service <https://myskills.ru/> - involves a single sign-on to the services of the Moscow Education Quality Center from any mobile device, access to the system is possible both by e-mail and social networks: Facebook, Vk, Google. You can use several login

methods: after registration, add additional login methods to your profile. It is possible to simulate a lesson by choosing assignments by topics, test work, video; distance learning can be arranged. All results are stored in your personal account, it is possible to obtain detailed analytics is available for each work completed and the task completed. The service is convenient in that it offers keys for checking/self-testing, there is a simulator. Not all topics have been fully represented yet.

The services of “Moscow Electronic School” - <https://uchebnik.mos.ru> and Russian Electronic School - <https://resh.edu.ru> - offer free access to materials during registration. It is possible to simulate a lesson/training session by selecting tasks according to difficulty level.

Digital educational resource for schools “YaKlass” - <https://www.yaklass.ru> - a digital educational resource for schools offers a certain competitive moment, to compare their achievements (class, school) with the achievements of others. At the same time, the content posted on these services needs additional substantive and methodological analysis, which includes, inter alia, studying the possibility of a differentiated approach, especially the work of a teacher in a particular class.

When the teacher uses digital educational resources, schoolchildren are given an opportunity of experiencing and utilizing various strategies of absorbing necessary information and comprehending various concepts through their practical and deliberate use. The biggest training effect can be derived from methods that provide for the use of digital sources not as the main but as an accessory educational resource, which is organically incorporated in the teacher’s education system. Given that, developers of electronic textbooks are willing to make their contents and structure easily adaptable to the use in native language teaching in various environments, to offer useful and entertaining assignments that help maintain continuous interest in the utilization of the opportunities provided by the native language.

Thus, skillfully using digital educational resources, the teacher boosts motivation of schoolchildren, manages their attention, provides them with new learning material and proposes learning strategies, effectively controls practical work, organizes their collaboration and actively involves children in the learning process, making sure of instant feedback.

Internet resources allow teachers and students to observe active processes in the Russian language, to study live, non-adapted language material, to evaluate it from the point of view of normative speech. This is especially important due to the fact that a significant portion of the teenager's verbal communication is “oral-written speech”, which contains an intentional distortion of the norms of the literary language, occasionalisms, slang.

Digital educational technologies such as digital humanities, media design, digital storytelling are relevant for teaching Russian language and literature, although they are not specifically designed for use in the educational process.

Discussions

At the ascertaining stage of the experiment, it was revealed that for the adolescents who are prone to deviant behavior, the indicator of the cognitive component of readiness for family life has medium level, the medium and low levels of family value dominate for the value-based component; low level of readiness for family life prevails in the behavioral component.

As a result of introducing pedagogical conditions into the educational process, there were identified significant positive changes for each component of readiness for family life in the experimental group, and no substantially significant differences were observed in the control group for this period of time.

There were revealed highly significant correlations of strong density between cognitive, value-based and behavioral components of readiness for family life among adolescents of the EG.

Conclusion

The study confirms the inefficiency of a complete rejection of traditional methodological resources in connection with the axiological component of Russian language and literature courses, as well as the relevance of research on the development of a new model for the examination of teaching and methodological kits (including in electronic form) taking into account updated federal educational standards and the basis of the concept of teaching the Russian language and literature in the Russian Federation (The Government of the Russian Federation, 2016); scientific and methodological support for teaching the Russian language and literature using digital educational resources; creation and use in the educational process of digital intelligent technologies and systems for processing large amounts of data.

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